

**THE GREAT PHILOSOPHER MIRZAJON SHEROZI TEACHER OF
MAVLONA YUSUF KARABAGI**

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Abstract: This article covers the socio-philosophical thought processes that developed in the territories of Central Asia and Azerbaijan in the 16th-17th centuries. In particular, information is provided about the activities and scientific heritage of the great philosopher Mirzajon Shirozi and his student Yusuf Karabaghi. Attention is paid to the difficulties in the scientific and cultural life of that period, religious contradictions, and the formation of scientific schools. The philosophical and theological works of Mirzajon Shirozi, as well as their influence on the territory of Central Asia, are analyzed.

Keywords: Central Asia, Azerbaijan, Yusuf Karabaghi, Mirzajon Shirozi, 16th-17th centuries, socio-philosophical thought, religious views, scientific heritage.

In the 16th-17th centuries, Azerbaijan experienced difficult times. Wars and persecutions were rampant. This was a difficult period in the history of Azerbaijan's cultural development. Sufi scholars Abu Talib Tabrizi and Mirza Muhammad Urdubodi were executed. Many scholars were persecuted. The famous philosopher and theologian Habibullah Mirzajon Shirazi al-Baqnavi was also born at that time, in the early 16th century, in the village of Baqnav near Shiraz. The exact date of his birth is unknown. He studied at the madrasa of Haji Kamoliddin Mahmud Shirazi in Shiraz. Habibullah Mirzajon Shirazi is known as a famous philosopher and theologian of his time. Since the Safavids paid great attention to science, education, and state building, Shiraz was very developed and became one of the scientific centers of its time. During the reign of Shah Tahmasib I, he was known as a famous philosopher and theologian. Since the Safavids paid great attention to science, education, and state building, Shiraz also developed considerably and became one of the cultural centers of its time. During that period (1524-1576), Mirzajon Shirazi taught theology, and people from different parts of Iran came to him to study. Most of them were famous in philosophical, pedagogical, and literary fields.

During the reign of Shah Ismail II (1576-1578), Mirzajon Shirazi went over to his supporters. For this reason, local scholars, philosophers, and theologians accused them of converting to Sunnism. Shirazi, however, did not pay attention

to such views, since he was under the protection of the king. Despite the opposition of the Shia clergy, Shah Ismail II forbade the first three Rightly Guided Caliphs - Abu Bakr, Umar, and Uthman (may Allah be pleased with them) - to openly curse in the streets and squares. The king ordered that Sunni clerics such as Mirza Makhdum Sharaf, Mawlana Mirzajan Shirazi, and Mir Makhdum Lola be treated with special respect and honor. However, accusations and persecutions did not stop. After the death of Shah Ismail II, such actions intensified. Therefore, Mirzajan Shirazi came to India from Shirazi in 988 AH (1584 AD) along with Yusuf Karabagh, who had come from Karabagh to study with him. He studied the secrets of mathematics in the city of Lork [1.68] .

At that time, Central Asia was considered one of the largest centers of enlightenment in the East. Along with local scholars, scholars and virtuous people who had left their homelands for various reasons lived and worked in Samarkand and Bukhara. Among these scholars, Mirzajon Shirozi held a special place [2.] . Even before arriving in Central Asia, Mirzajon Shirozi met Mir Baba Kokaldash, the brother of Abdulla Khan II, a high-ranking official, in Balkh. At his invitation, accompanied by Yusuf Karabogi, he first went to Samarkand and then to Bukhara. Mirzajon Shirozi taught at the Khiyabon madrasah built by Abdulla Khan in Bukhara. His arrival here was not welcomed by local religious figures. Differences arose between the opinions of foreign scholars and the views of local scholars. The debate that took place in the Khiyabon mosque between the scholars led by Amir Sadriddin Bukhari and Mirzajon Shirozi soon became famous. Uzbek scholar M. Nuriddinov writes in his book "From the History of Socio-Philosophical Thought in Central Asia in the 16th-17th Centuries": "Mirzajon Shirazi's scope of activity was very wide. But he was primarily engaged in philosophy. He achieved great success in the system of logic. His works as a theologian gained fame, he knew theology deeply. His name was mentioned along with ten scholars who were famous in those times - al-Farabi, Ibn Sina, Abu Walid ibn Rushd, Abu Bark as-Safi, Nasir al-Din Tusi, Shahobiddin al-Maqtul, Qutbiddin ash-Shirvani, Jalaluddin Davvani, Muhammad Zohid al-Hirovi and others"[3.28]. Mirzajon Shirazi al-Baqnavi died in 1585 in Bukhara during the reign of Abdullakhan II. 15 works by Mirzajon Shirazi are kept in the Abu Raykhan Beruni Center for Oriental Manuscripts. His books are also found in Egyptian libraries. We have considered it appropriate to cite the original titles of the works stored at the center:

1. "Commentary and additions to Ibn Sina's "Book of Instructions and Notes"" ("Kitabul isharat vat-takbihat"). The author dedicated this work to the

Shaybanid prince Abul Muzaffar Sultan Shah Ismail Bahadir Khan. Nasir al-Din Tusi and Fakhr al-Din al-Razi wrote different commentaries on Ibn Sina's work. Muhammad al-Razi at-Takhtani also wrote comments in order to reconcile them. Mirzajon Shirazi in this work is more inclined towards Takhtani.

2. Commentary and additions to "The Wisdom of the Fountain" ("Hashiya ala sharhi hikmatil-'ayn"). Commentary (on metaphysics and physics) on the treatise "The Wisdom of the Fountain" ("Hikmatil 'ayn") by Najimiddin Ali Qazvini, a student of Nasir al-Din Tusi.

3. "Commentary and Additions to the Spread of Light" ("Hashiyat ala tasdiqati sharhil matole"). Written about the treatise "The Spread of Light" by Sirajuddin Abus-Sano bin Bakr al-Urmawi.

4. Commentary and additions to the work "Proving Necessary Things" ("Khashiyat bar risola-i isboti wajib"). Commentary on the work of the 15th century philosopher and theologian Alaluddin Davwani.

5. "Addition to the Commentary on the Permanent Places" ("Hashiya bar sharhi mawakif"). A commentary on the work of Abdurrahman al-I'ji.

6. Additions to the commentary on the "Foundation of Beliefs" ("Khashiyat sharhi tadjridul aqid"). N. Tusi's "Commentary on Beliefs" It was written as a supplement to the work "I", based on the commentary of Jalaluddin Davvani.

7. "Additions on the Broadness" ("Khashiyat alal mutawwal"). A commentary on the third part of al-Khwarizmi's three-part work "Miftah ul-ulum" (Key to the Sciences).

8. "A Treatise on the Separation of Sciences" ("Amuzadjul Ulum". Consists of 7-8 pages.

9. "Examples of the Sciences" ("Anmuzadjul funun"). This is the only copy and is a list written in Arabic. The writing is indecipherable.

10. "Seven Studies on the Seven Denials" ("Sab'atu abkhasin-al-mutaallika bis-sawalib as-sab'a").

11. "Treatise on Reflections" ("Fi aksil mustava").

12. Explanation of the issues mentioned in the "Conditions" section of the benefits of Diyaiyya ("Hashiyatun ala mabkhasi halal li-fawaid ad-Diyaiyya"). About the commentary written by Abdurrahman Jami on Ibn al-Hajib's book "al-Kofiya" on Arabic grammar.

13. "Research treatise on the issues of perceiving Allah" ("Rasail dar takhniki masail-i ru'yo"). Written in Persian on religious-Sufi views.

14. A clip from the discussion between Mirzajon Shirazi and Amir Sadriddin Bukhari on the commentary of Surah Fath.

15. "About the beginning of Surah Al-Fath."

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